

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Urmonova Nigoraxon Alijonova

QANDLI DIABET KASALLIGINING KELIB CHIQISHI VA TABIIY USULLAR BILAN DAVOLASH

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/OKTABR

